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Review Article

A Review: Formulation of Herbal Lozenges for Increasing platelet Counts

Lina Durbale*, Bhagyashri Meshram, Vaibhav Jain

G. H Raison University, Bachelor of pharmacy, Saikheda,, M.P - 48337

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ABSTRACT

This article investigates the formulation techniques used in formulating herbal lozenges from leaf of Carica papaya and fruit of kiwi. Considering the medicinal properties of these botanical sources the review delves into the selection of suitable excipients to optimize the therapeutic efficacy and mask the organoleptic properties to enhance the patients compliance. Carica papaya leaf has been scientifically studied for various therapeutic activities like antibacterial, antioxidant, antipyretic, insecticidal, antimicrobial, antimolluscal etc. The medicinal properties of fruit and other parts of papaya are well known in the different system of traditional medicine including Ayurveda. Kiwi fruit (Actinidia deliciosa) belongs to the family Actinidiaceae and genus Actinidia. It is one of the most commercialized fruits on the international front and is loaded with many nutrients such as vitamins, minerals, and phytochemicals, and its parts are well recognized for their medicinal and therapeutic properties against diseases associated with the cardiovascular system, diabetes, kidney problems, cancer, digestive disorders, bone, and eye problems Besides these, kiwi fruit also finds its traditional application in the effective treatment of edema, hepatitis, kidney problems, rheumatoid arthralgia, and microbial infections. The fiber present in kiwi fruit favors its water retention capacity which further aids in decreasing the transit time and maintains gastrointestinal health of the individual. By formulating this in lozenge dosage form will increase the its efficacy as lozenges are one of the widely used dosage forms. The benefits of the medicated lozenges is they increase the retention time of the dosage form in oral cavity which increases bioavailability, reduces gastric irritation and bypasses first pass metabolism.

INTRODUCTION

Carica papaya is such a Marvelous plant, possesses various medicinal properties making it unique among other 22 species of family Caricaceae. The

various parts of this plant are used for curing different ailments. Leaves are the most useful part among all used parts for the medicinal purpose. activities on leaves are reported with scientific

***Corresponding Author:** Lina Durbale

Address: G. H Raison University, Bachelor of pharmacy, Saikheda, M.P - 48337

Email ✉: leenadurbale2@gmail.com

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data recently. It normalizes the pulse rate in fever and acts as diuretic when administered as decoction. It is attributed to exterminate cough and respiratory, liver and spleen related diseases as well as useful in loss of appetite and oedema. Leaves of *Carica papaya* are used in severe jaundice, to expel guinea worm, as a poultice, in fracture healing, constipation and indigestion. It has been used to treat oral candidosis, malaria, dengue, yellow fever and as a diuretic in dengue related anaemic. Kiwi fruit belongs to the family of Actinidiaceae and genus Actinidia. The other names of kiwi fruit are Macaque peach, Mihoutau, and Chinese gooseberry. It is nearly 3 inches long and has a brown hairy peel containing green flesh and white pulp in the centre with many minute black edible seeds. It is a potent source of vitamins such as vitamins A, B, C, E, and K and notably appreciable levels of dietary fibre, folate, potassium, and other minerals. It consists of various phytochemicals such as carotenoids, flavonoids, anthocyanins, and lutein. It possesses various pharmacological properties such as anti-cancerous, anti-diabetic, antifertility, hepatoprotective, antiulcer, prevention of cataracts, and macular degeneration. Owing to the several medicinal properties of kiwi fruit, it has become awfully popular. Lozenges are the flavoured medicated dosage forms intended to be sucked and held in the mouth or pharynx containing one or more medicaments usually in the sweetened base. Lozenges are intended to relieve oropharyngeal symptoms, which are commonly caused by local infections and also for systemic effect provided the drug is well absorbed through the buccal linings or when it is swallowed. Lozenges are used for patients who cannot swallow solid oral dosage forms as well as for medications designed to be released slowly to yield a constant level of drug in the oral cavity or to bathe the throat tissues in a solution of the drug. Drugs often incorporated into lozenges include

analgesics, anesthetics, antimicrobials, antiseptics, etc however this is by no means an exhaustive list as many other drugs may lend themselves to delivery by a lozenge. As well, both single and multiingredient lozenges can be compounded, depending on the particular patient's needs.

Drug profile

Leaf of *Carica papaya*

Fig. no 1 Visual representation of leaf of *Carica papaya*

The use of medicinal plants in disease prevention and treatment has been around for many generations worldwide and some of them have been scientifically proven. Various medicinal plants, especially those with antiviral activity have drawn interest from researchers to formulate new medicinal drugs for infectious diseases around the world. Like other plants, *Carica papaya* L. has a high content of phytochemicals that not only have beneficial food nutritional values but also medicinal potential. Its leaves contain alkaloids, flavonoids, phenolic acids, saponin, amino acids, organic acids, vitamins, minerals, carbohydrates and carotenoids.. This plant is very famous for its edible fruit to relieve constipation. Its seeds can be pounded and then ingested to treat intestinal worms. Toothache, corns and warts can be treated by topically applying its sap. Recently, the *C. papaya*, particularly its leaf part, has attracted wide attention for its potential use in dengue treatment.

Taxonomical Classification

Table 1: Taxonomical Classification of Papaya

Domain	Flowering plant
Kingdom	Plantae
Sub Kingdom	Tracheobionta
Class	Magnoliopsida
Subclass	Dilleniidae
Superdivision	Spermatophyta
Phyllum	Steptophyta
Order	Brassicales
Family	Caricaceae
Genus	<i>Carica</i>
Botanical Name	<i>Carica papaya</i> Linn

Therapeutic uses

The therapeutic use of carica papaya L. to increase platelet count, aid in cancer treatment, prevent heart burn, heal fever, reduce skin problems, treats diabetes, treat high blood pressure, boost immune system, anti-inflammatory, use in dengue treatment etc.

Kiwi

Fig no.2 Visual representation of kiwi fruit (Actinidia)

In India kiwi is mostly grown in the mild hills of Himachal Pradesh, Arunachal Pradesh, Uttar Pradesh, Sikkim, Meghalaya, Kerela. The kiwi fruit is healthy and contain many vitamins and minerals, nutritive and medicinal value. Kiwi are rich in vitamin A, vitamin B, vitamin C, vitamin E, vitamin K, potassium, fiber, carotenoids, flavonoids, anthocyanins, and lutein. Kiwi fruit is use in salad, juice, DIY face mask and maintain beautiful skin, it is mostly use in dengue treatment for increase platelet counts.

Taxonomical Classification

Table 2: Taxonomical Classification of Kiwi Fruit

Kingdom	Plantae
Division	Magnoliophyta
Class	Magnoliopsida
Subclass	Magnoliidae
Order	Ericales
Superorder	Asteranae
Family	Actinidiaceae
Genus	<i>Actinidia</i>

Therapeutic uses

The therapeutic use of kiwi fruit is to increase platelet count, boost immune system, helps in controlling diabetics, helps in digestion, manage blood pressure, improve heart health, helps to fight cancer, helps to clear out toxins, good for eye health, maintain alkaline balance, beneficial for weight loss, protects against DNA damage, good for asthma, etc.

Lozenges

The introduction to herbal lozenges sets the stage for understanding these medicinal formulations. Herbal lozenges, also known as herbal throat lozenges or herbal troches, represent a distinctive category of pharmaceutical and natural health products designed for oral administration. Unlike traditional tablets or capsules, lozenges are solid dosage forms intended to dissolve or disintegrate slowly in the mouth, allowing for the gradual release of active ingredients. The appeal of herbal lozenges lies in their dual functionality – not only do they serve as a convenient and palatable means of delivering therapeutic compounds, but they also address conditions affecting the oral and throat regions. Herbal ingredients, derived from plants with known medicinal properties, contribute not only to the flavor but also to the potential health benefits of these lozenges. This introduction aims to provide a foundational understanding of herbal lozenges, emphasizing their unique attributes,

modes of action, and the growing interest in utilizing herbal components for their diverse therapeutic potential. As consumers seek natural alternatives, herbal lozenges stand at the intersection of traditional knowledge and contemporary pharmaceutical innovation, offering a promising avenue for both symptomatic relief and holistic wellness.

Advantages and disadvantages of medicated lozenges

Lozenges offer many advantages to formulation scientists like they avoid first pass metabolism, thus increase in bioavailability can be used for purpose of both local and systemic effect through buccal mucosa, offer better patient compliance can be given to those patients who have difficulty in swallowing and easy to manufacture and store. Medicated lozenges also have drawbacks like nonubiquitous distribution of drug within saliva for local therapy and possible draining of drug from oral cavity to stomach along with saliva.

TYPES OF LOZENGES

Classification of Lozenges

Lozenges can be classified into various classes based on various methods like

A. According to the site of action

- a Local effect Ex. Antiseptics, Decongestants.
- b Systemic effect Ex. Vitamins, Nicotine.

B. According to texture and composition-

a. Chewy or caramel based medicated lozenges

These are the dosage form in which medicament is incorporated into a caramel base which is chewed instead of being dissolved in mouth. Most formulations are based on the glycerinated gelatin suppository formula which consists of glycerin, gelatin, and water. These lozenges are often highly fruit flavoured and may have a slightly acidic taste to cover the acid taste of the glycerin.

b. Compressed tablet lozenges

When the active ingredient is heat sensitive, it may be prepared by compression. The granulation method is similar to that used for any compressed

tablet. These tablets differ from conventional tablets in terms of organoleptic property, non-disintegrating characteristics and slower dissolution profiles.

c. Soft lozenges

They are either meant for chewing or for slow drug release in mouth. They can be made from PEG 1000 or 1450, chocolate or sugar-acacia base while some soft candy formulations can also contain acacia and silica gel. Acacia is used to provide texture and smoothness and silica gel is used as a suspending agent to avoid settling of materials to the bottom of the mold cavity during the cooling. The formulation requires heating process at about 50 °C, hence is only suitable to heat resistant ingredients.

d. Hard lozenges

These are mixtures of sugar and other carbohydrates in an amorphous (non crystalline) or glassy state. They can also be regarded as solid syrups of sugars. The moisture content and weight of hard candy lozenge should be in between, 0.5 - 1.5% and 1.5-4.5 g respectively. These should undergo a slow and uniform dissolution or erosion over 5- 10 min., and they should not disintegrate.

IDEAL PROPERTIES OF LOZENGE

1. Is a solid preparation consisting of sugar and gum, the latter giving strength and cohesiveness to the lozenge
2. Facilitating slow release of the medicament.
3. It is used to medicate the mouth and throat for the slow administration in digestion or cough remedies.
4. It is intended to dissolve slowly in the mouth to temporarily suppress the cough, and lubricate and soothe irritated tissues of the throat.
5. Some have medications that help fight colds, and most have anaesthetic to help ease the pain.
6. Lozenges also contain menthol or eucalyptus, which can help cool and sooth the throat.

Method of preparation of medicated Lozenges

Technique used → heating and congealing.

In this hard lozenge, sugar syrup was prepared by blending sugar and water. Sugar was dissolved in a little amount of water and warmed it to 110°C till sugar breaks down totally forming clear thick syrup. To slow the rate of dissolution, polymers such as HPMC and PEGs may be added. Another type of hard lozenges may be made of compressed powders. Large compressed tablet that is slowly dissolved in the mouth. The tablet base material is made of dextrose, povidone and MCC. Soft lozenges are often made using PEGs of sufficient molecular weight to provide slow dissolution in the saliva. Chewable lozenges are typically based on glycerinated gelatin, a base of glycerin . gelatin and water. This drug can be mixed with API, acacia, sweetening agent, flavouring agent.

Evaluation parameters.

a. pH :-

A pH meter is an instrument used to measure hydrogen ion activity in solution . the degree of hydrogen ion activity is ultimately expressed as pH level, which generally ranges from 1 to 14.

- Acidic solution, $\text{pH} < 7$
- Neutral solution, $\text{pH} = 7$
- Basic solution, $\text{pH} > 7$.

b. Weight variation :-

The weight variation test was carried out 20 lozenges randomly by weighing each lozenges individually and their was calculated.

c. Disintegration time :-

Disintegration time of six Lozenges was calculated using disintegration test apparatus. Each lozenges was subjected into the tube of the basket rack assembly of the disintegration apparatus without disc. The assembly was positioned in the beaker containing disintegration media maintained at $37 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ and the time required for complete disintegration, was recorded as disintegration time.

d. Dissolution time :-

Dissolution is the process in which a substance from a solution. Dissolution testing measures the extent and rate of solution formation from dosages from, such as lozenges, tablet, capsule, ointment, etc, the dissolution of a drug is important for it bioavailability and therapeutic effectiveness.

e. Hardness :-

Hardness of the lozenges was determine using Monsanto hardness tester. The lozenges to be tested was placed between the spindle and anvil, and a desired pressure was needed to hold the lozenges in position followed by moving the screw knob in clockwise direction until the lozenges was broken. The reading was noted, that indicates the pressure needed to break the lozenges which was indicated in Kg/cm^2 .

f. Friability :-

10 lozenges were weighed and placed in the Roche friabilator test apparatus which is then subjected to rolling for repeated shocks, resulting from free falls within the apparatus. After 100 revolutions the lozenges were de-dusted and weighted again. The lozenges that less than 1% weight were considered to be complaint. The Friability from the expression.

g. Diameter and thickness :-

Diameter and thickness of the five tablet was determined by using Venier calliper.

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